

WAVE GROUP EFFECTS ON OFFSHORE STRUCTURES

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ABSTRACT

The effect of wave groups and an associated forced second-order wave system on a fixed offshore structure is examined analytically. Based on the modified Morison's equation approach, the dynamic response of a single degree of freedom, fixed offshore structure is investigated using a primary wave system with and without the second-order wave system. By comparing the results, it is found that the second-order wave system can significantly affect structural response. This is particularly true of structures in shallow water.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most methods for calculating the dynamic response of off-shore structures use a spectrum of waves as the forcing function. Examples include the works of Chakrabarti and Cotter [1], Chung et al. [2], Kirk and Etok [5], Pinkster [8], and Vandiver [9]. If the spectrum is reasonably narrow, then fairly well-defined "wave groups" can result. For design purposes, it is important to consider the effect of the largest waves in the groups since they can cause structural damage. An approach based on individual waves of the same size and dispersed throughout a wave train is a less severe case.

Longuet-Higgins [6] and Longuet-Higgins and Stewart [7] have shown that wave groups drive a coupled, second-order wave system. The effect of this wave theory on the dynamic response of a fixed offshore structure is analytically investigated in this paper. Generally the determination of wave loads on offshore structures is based on two major techniques. For large structures, the scattering of the incident waves is considered and a diffraction theory is employed. The wave loads on small members of offshore structures are usually determined by applying Morison's equation, which includes drag and inertia force components. For simplicity, a single degree of freedom structure with negligible wave scattering is considered. Also, the wave loads are determined by applying the modified Morison equation.

2. WAVE GROUP THEORY

The wave group model of Longuet-Higgins and Stewart is illustrated in Figure 1. Its basic components include a primary wave system and a second-order wave system that is always out of phase with the group amplitude. This phenomenon is illustrated in Figure 1 where the second-order wave trough is shown at the wave group maxima and the second-order wave crest at the wave group minima.

Figure 1. Wave due to second-order forced wave system in a wave group.

In their papers, Longuet-Higgins and Stewart investigate two cases: (1) the primary waves are relatively short compared to the depth and (2) the primary waves are not necessarily short, but the "group length" is long compared to the depth. In this paper, the latter case's effect on structural response will be investigated, since it is the most significant from wave force considerations.

The mathematical models of the wave group components are given below and are based on the coordinate system shown in Figure 1.

Primary Wave System

The velocity potential, ϕ_1 , water surface, σ_1 , horizontal velocity, u_1 , and acceleration, \dot{u}_1 , for the primary wave system are

$$\phi_1(x, z, t) = \frac{a_1 \sigma}{k} \frac{\cosh k(b+z)}{\sinh kb} \sin(kx - \sigma t) \quad (1)$$

$$\eta_1(x, t) = a_1 \cos(kx - \sigma t) \quad (2)$$

$$u_1(x, z, t) = \frac{\partial \phi_1}{\partial x} = a_1 \sigma \frac{\cosh k(b+z)}{\sinh kb} \cos(kx - \sigma t) \quad (3)$$

$$\dot{u}_1(x, z, t) = \frac{\partial u_1}{\partial t} = a_1 \sigma^2 \frac{\cosh k(b+z)}{\sinh kb} \sin(kx - \sigma t) \quad (4)$$

where k is the wave number, σ is the angular frequency, h is the water depth, and a_1 is the "local" wave amplitude dependent on x .

Second-Order Wave System

Velocity potential, ϕ_2 , for the second-order wave system is

$$\phi_2(x, z, t) = -a_2 C_g \frac{\cosh \Delta k(b+z)}{\sinh \Delta kb} \sin \Delta k(x - C_g t) \quad (5)$$

where C_g is the group velocity, Δk is the "group" wave number and a_2 is given by

$$a_2 = \frac{(a_{1\max}^2 - a_{1\min}^2)}{4b \left(1 - \frac{C_g^2}{gb}\right)} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2kb}{\sinh 2kb} \right) \quad (6)$$

Here, $a_{1\max}$ is the maximum displacement of the wave envelope and $a_{1\min}$ the minimum displacement of the wave envelope. Both parameters are shown in Figure 1.

The water surface, η_2 , for the second-order wave system is given as

$$\eta_2(x, t) = -a_2 \cos \Delta k(x - C_g t) \quad (7)$$

When $\cos \Delta k(x - C_g t) = 1$, η_1 is a maximum and η_2 a minimum.

The horizontal velocity, u_2 , and acceleration, \dot{u}_2 , of the second-order wave system are given as

$$u_2(x, z, t) = \frac{\partial \phi_2}{\partial x} = -a_2 C_g \Delta k \frac{\cosh \Delta k(b+z)}{\sinh \Delta kb} \cos \Delta k(x - C_g t) \quad (8)$$

and

$$\dot{u}_2(x, z, t) = \frac{\partial u_2}{\partial t} = -a_2 C_g^2 \Delta k^2 \frac{\cosh \Delta k(b+z)}{\sinh \Delta kb} \sin \Delta k(x - C_g t) \quad (9)$$

which are both seen to be negative when the wave envelope is a maximum.

Since the dynamic response of an offshore structure would be affected by the waves forming the extremes of the wave envelopes, the effect of these second-order waves are considered in this paper.

3. EFFECT OF SECOND-ORDER WAVE SYSTEM ON STRUCTURES

For a generalized, single degree of freedom system of a fixed offshore structure, the equation of motion is

$$M\ddot{X}(t) + C\dot{X}(t) + KX(t) = F_W(t) \quad (10)$$

where M is the mass of the structure, C the internal structural damping, K the structural stiffness, X , \dot{X} and \ddot{X} are, respectively, the displacement, velocity, and acceleration of the structure and $F_W(t)$ is the external force acting on the structure. All the above quan-

ties are based on a unit length of the structures. $F_W(t)$ is represented by the modified Morison's equation:

$$F_W(t) = \frac{\rho}{2} C_D D |u(t) - \dot{X}(t)| [u(t) - \dot{X}(t)] + \rho \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \dot{u}(t) + \rho (C_M - 1) \frac{\pi D^2}{4} [\dot{u}(t) - \ddot{X}(t)] \quad (11)$$

where C_D is the drag coefficient, C_M the inertia coefficient, $(C_M - 1)$ the added mass coefficient, ρ the mass density of water, D the pile diameter, u the local water particle velocity, and \dot{u} the acceleration.

For most wave-loading conditions, the water particle velocity is much larger than that of the structure. Hence, the following approximation of Dao and Penzin [3] can be made.

$$|u(t) - \dot{X}(t)| [u(t) - \dot{X}(t)] \approx u(t) |u(t)| - 2 |u(t)| \dot{X}(t) \quad (12)$$

Inserting Eqs. (11) and (12) into Eq. (10), then, gives the equation of motion as

$$\left[M + (C_M - 1) \rho \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \right] \ddot{X}(t) + C \dot{X}(t) + \rho C_D D |u(t)| \dot{X}(t) + KX(t) = \frac{\rho}{2} C_D D u(t) |u(t)| + \rho C_M \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \dot{u}(t) \quad (13)$$

Drag Force Effects

To find the total displacement of the structure due to drag force, *i.e.*, the first term on the right side of Eq. (13), the crest phase of the primary wave system must be selected. By integrating Eq. (13) from the ocean bottom ($z = -h$) up to the mean free surface, ($z = 0$), the total displacement of the structure due to drag force and the primary wave system (X_{DWO}^*) is

$$X_{DWO}^* = \frac{\rho}{2K^*} C_D D a_{1\max}^2 \frac{\sigma^2}{\sinh^2 kb} \left(\frac{\sinh 2kb + 2kb}{4k} \right) \quad (14)$$

where K^* is the total structure stiffness.

The total displacement of the structure due to drag force with the primary and second-order wave systems (X_{DW}^*) is

$$X_{DW}^* = \frac{\rho}{2K^*} C_D D \left\{ a_{1\max}^2 \frac{\sigma^2}{\sinh^2 kb} \frac{(\sinh 2kb + 2kb)}{4k} - 2 \frac{a_{1\max} a_2 \sigma C_g \Delta k}{\sinh kb \sinh \Delta kb} \left(\frac{k \sinh kb \cosh \Delta kb - \Delta k \cosh kb \sinh \Delta kb}{k^2 - \Delta k^2} \right) + a_2^2 C_g \Delta k \frac{(\sinh 2\Delta kb + 2\Delta kb)}{4(\sinh \Delta kb)^2} \right\} \quad (15)$$

where a_1 in Eqs. (14) and (15) has been taken as the maximum value of the envelope.

Inertia Force Effects

The total displacement of the structure due to inertia force, *i.e.*, the second term on the right side of Eq. (13), occurs at the mean water level. By integrating Eq. (13) from the ocean bottom ($z = -h$) up to the mean free surface ($z = 0$), the total displacement of the structure due to inertia force without (X_{Iw}^*) and with (X_{Iw}^*) the effect of second-order wave system is computed as

$$X_{Iw}^* = \frac{\rho}{K^* C_M} \frac{\pi D^2}{4} a_1 \frac{\sigma^2}{k} \quad (16)$$

and

$$X_{Iw}^* = \frac{\rho}{K^* C_M} \frac{\pi D^2}{4} \left[a_1 \frac{\sigma^2}{k} - a_2 C_g^2 \Delta k \right] \quad (17)$$

Second-Order Wave System Effects

The total displacement of the structure due to the second-order wave system increases with decreasing water depth because the primary wave system transfers energy into the second-order wave system. In discussing this effect a_{wO} and a_w will denote, respectively, the primary wave system amplitudes without and with the energy transfer to the second-order wave system taken into account, *i.e.*, $a_{wO} > a_w$.

The ratio, R_{DX} , of the total displacement of the structure due to drag force with and without the presence of the second-order wave system is obtained by dividing Eq. (15) by Eq. (14):

$$R_{DX} = \frac{X_{Dw}^*}{X_{Dwo}^*} = \left(\frac{a_w}{a_{wO}} \right)^2 (1 - P_1 + P_2) \quad (18)$$

where

$$P_1 = \frac{a_w}{2b} \left\{ \frac{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2kb}{\sinh 2kb}}{1 - \frac{C_g^2}{gb}} \right\} \frac{\tanh kb}{kb} \quad (19)$$

and

$$P_2 = \frac{1}{32} \left(\frac{a_w}{b} \right)^2 \left\{ \frac{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2kb}{\sinh 2kb}}{1 - \frac{C_g^2}{gb}} \right\}^2 \left(1 + \frac{2kb}{\sinh 2kb} \right) \frac{\tanh kb}{kb} \quad (20)$$

In deriving Eq. (18) it is assumed that $k \gg \Delta k$ and that $\Delta kh \ll 1$.

Similarly, the ratio of the total displacement of the structure due to inertia force with and without the presence of the second-order wave system, R_{IX} , is

$$R_{IX} = \frac{X_{Iw}^*}{X_{Iwo}^*} = \left(\frac{a_w}{a_{wO}} \right) (1 - Q) \quad (21)$$

where

$$Q = \frac{a_w}{16b} \left\{ \frac{\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2kb}{\sinh 2kb}}{1 - \frac{C_g^2}{gb}} \right\} \left(1 + \frac{2kb}{\sinh 2kb} \right)^2 \frac{\Delta k}{k} \quad (22)$$

To evaluate the importance of the total displacement of the structure due to the second-order wave system (Eqs. (18) and (21)), it is necessary to establish the ratio, a_w/a_{wO} , *i.e.*, the effect of energy transfer from the primary to the second-order wave system. Dean [4] derived the ratios, a_w/a_{wO} and a_2/a_{wO} , by using the energy flux conservation between the primary wave system with and without the second-order wave system. They are given as:

$$\zeta = \frac{a_w}{a_{wO}} = \sqrt{\frac{-1 + \sqrt{1 + 8F^2 \left(\frac{a_{wO}}{b} \right)^2}}{4F^2 \left(\frac{a_{wO}}{b} \right)}} \quad (23)$$

where

$$F \left(\frac{b}{L_o} \right) = \frac{1}{4 \left(1 - \frac{C_g^2}{gb} \right)} \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{2kb}{\sinh 2kb} \right) \quad (24)$$

and

$$\frac{a_2}{a_{wO}} = \zeta^2 \frac{a_{wO}}{b} F \left(\frac{b}{L_o} \right) \quad (25)$$

4. RESULTS

Figure 2 shows the variations of a_w/a_{wO} and a_2/a_{wO} for $a_{wO} = 0.25$ and 1.0 of the breaking value, a_{wOB} . It is interesting that the second-order wave amplitude exceeds the primary wave amplitude in shallow water. In reality, the theory of the second-order wave system is valid for only relatively small second-order wave amplitudes, especially in shallow water. Therefore, a high-order wave theory is necessary if good accuracy is required. For discussion purposes, the results are considered valid if the ratio a_2/a_{wO} is on the order of 0.10 to 0.20.

The ratio, R_{DX} , for $a_{wO} = 0.25$ and 1.0 of the breaking value is shown in Figure 3. It is seen that this ratio varies significantly in shallow water. If the ratio $a_2/a_{wO} = 0.1$ is taken, the corresponding R_{DX} values are 0.79 and 0.88 for relative breaking wave amplitudes of 0.25 and 1.0, respectively. A value of $a_2/a_{wO} = 0.2$

yields values of $R_{DX} = 0.61$ for $a_{WO} = 0.25 A_{WOB}$ and 0.65 for $A_{WO} = A_{WOB}$.

Figure 4 gives the ratio R_{IX} versus relative depth for $\Delta k/k = 0.1$ (e.g., the wave length of the primary wave system and the wave group are 100 m and 1 km) and $a_{WO} = 0.25 a_{WOB}$ and a_{WOB} . It is seen that this ratio is small in the shallow-water range and approaches unity in deep water. The reduction of R_{IX} is from 2 to 6% as the second-order amplitude is from 10 to 20% of the primary wave system.

5. CONCLUSIONS

The effect of second-order wave system can significantly affect the dynamic response of fixed offshore structures. This is particularly true in shallow water. Structural response due to drag force and inertia force from the combined effects of the primary and the second-order wave systems are found to be reduced at the wave crest position and the mean water level. The reduction of structural response due to inertia force is much smaller than that due to drag force because the drag force includes a square term. The structural response due to drag force at the trough position has not been shown in the results. Clearly, the results would be an increase of structural response at the trough phase position. However, it is because the magnitude of the structural response at crest position is greater than that at trough position due to the additional submergence of piling at the crest position. Therefore, only the crest position was considered.

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Figure 2. Variation of a_w/a_{WO} and a_2/a_{WO} with h/L_0 for $a_{WO}/A_{WOB} = 0.25$ and 1.0 .

Figure 3. Ratio of total displacement of structures due to drag force for the wave crest position.

Figure 4. Ratio of total displacement of structures due to inertia force for the mean water level position and $\Delta k/k = 0.1$.

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